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Review Article

**PROPHYLACTIC MEDICATIONS OF THROMBOSIS
FOLLOWING MAJOR SURGERY: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW**Abdullah Talal Almaghrabi ¹, Nouf Hassan Abukhalid ¹, Waleed Mohammed Alghamdi ¹, Salah Mohammed B Almuyidi ²¹Faculty of Medicine, University of Debrecen, ²College of Medicine, Taif University, Saudi Arabia**Abstract:**

Introduction: Oral anticoagulants can be used for prevention and treatment of thrombosis. New oral anticoagulants such as rivaroxaban provide more consistent and predictable anticoagulation than warfarin as they are direct factor Xa inhibitor. The aim of this review is to evaluate the evidence of using prophylactic medications to prevent thromboembolism in hospitalized patients.

Methods: An electronic search in MEDLINE was conducted with no limits applied regarding age of the patients or the type of injury because some of studied medications are relatively recent and any available study would add significantly to the review. Included studies were aimed to evaluate the use of prophylactic medications to prevent thromboembolism in hospitalized patients who have been indicated to major surgical interventions. Any study met these inclusion criteria were eligible in this review.

Results: The MEDLINE search resulted in 97 studies which underwent screening of the eligibility criteria and 11 studies met the inclusion criteria. The thromboprophylaxis effect was higher when rivaroxaban compared to no treatment or placebo, while no significant differences were found when rivaroxaban, dalteparin or low-molecular-weight heparin compared to placebo. Moreover, when medications compared to each other, no significant difference in thromboprophylaxis effect was reported in many included studies. Only edoxaban and dabigatran were found superior to enoxaparin by two included studies.

Conclusion: This review showed that new oral anticoagulants could be effective in reducing risk of thrombosis particularly in high-risk patients subjected to major surgery.

Keywords: Thrombosis, Prevention, Drugs, Surgery, Anti-coagulants.

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INTRODUCTION:

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is a common condition following injury and immobilization (1). Thromboprophylaxis has been prescribed for all hospitalized patients at higher risk of venous thromboembolism (VTE) (2). Venous thromboembolism remains the main source of morbidity and mortality among hospitalized patients (3, 4), while it is thought to be the most preventable risk factor (4). Interventions used to reduce the rate of hospitalization-related VTE focused on distinguishing patients in risk for developing VTE, and after that guaranteeing the utilization of a prophylactic regimen (5). Regardless of these efforts, the frequency of VTE remains high (6), more than half of medical facility-related VTE are attributed to prophylaxis failure, though studies have recognized risk factors for thromboprophylaxis failure (3, 4).

When inadequate thromboprophylaxis is administered, the possibility of hospital-related VTE in inpatients is as high as 25% which elevated to 40%-60% in high risk patients such as congestive heart failure and stroke (7). Recently, oral anticoagulants can be used for prevention and treatment of thrombosis [1]. Dabigatran etexilate is an oral, direct thrombin inhibitor for prevention and treatment of venous and arterial thromboembolic diseases. The effectiveness comes from the active compound dabigatran prodrug, which binds to thrombin with a high affinity and specificity directly [2]. New oral anticoagulants such as rivaroxaban provide more consistent and predictable anticoagulation than warfarin as they are direct factor Xa inhibitor. The aim of this review is to evaluate the evidence of using prophylactic medications to prevent thromboembolism in hospitalized patients.

METHODS:

An electronic search in MEDLINE was conducted using search strategy (thromboprophylaxis) and (surgery OR preoperative OR postoperative OR perioperative). There were no exclusion criteria applied regarding years of publication however, included studies were clinical trials published in English language. Population characteristics include patients hospitalized for major surgical interventions. No limits were applied regarding age of the patients or the type of spine injury because some of studied medications are relatively recent and any available study would add significantly to the review. Included studies were aimed to evaluate the use of prophylactic medications to prevent thromboembolism in hospitalized patients who have been indicated to major surgical interventions. Any study met these inclusion criteria were eligible to be selected during the primary screening stage when the researcher read the titles and abstracts of

the articles and based on this reading and they excluded articles which were irrelevant (have different aim), or duplicated. The reference list of this review was screened for relevant studies. Then the full texts of the eligible studies were retrieved and further studies with inconsistent outcomes were excluded. The data about important characteristics and outcomes of included studies were extracted using data extraction sheet and summary of the findings was demonstrated in the table. The findings of the included studies were discussed in a qualitative approach and the effectiveness of the medications was highlighted.

RESULTS:

The MEDLINE search resulted in 97 studies which underwent screening of the eligibility criteria and 11 studies met the inclusion criteria. All the included studies were clinical trials with a sample size ranged from 80 in Li et al. study [3] to 4413 in a multinational, randomized, double-blind parallel group clinical trial [4]. The mean age of the included patients varied from 44.9 in Camporese et al. [5] 76.1 in Li et al. study [3]. The type of surgical intervention was knee surgery in five included studies [5-9], total hip arthroplasty in three studies [10-12], or other interventions such as major laparotomy [4], femoral surgical repair of fractures in femoral neck [3], tibia, fibula or ankle [13]. The underlying risk factors of thrombosis among patients of included studies were mainly obesity which was reported in six included studies [4-7,11,12], while hypertension was reported in four studies [3,5,9,10]. Additionally, diabetes was a common risk factor demonstrated in four studies [3,5,9,10], while hormonal studies was studied as a risk factor in some included studies [4,5,7]. Other studied risk factors included smoking [3,7], coronary heart disease [9], hyperlipidemia [5,10], chronic heart or respiratory failure [4].

Among included studies, rivaroxaban was assessed as a thromboprophylaxis in four include studies [3,5,8,9] when it was compared to enoxaparin [9], no treatment [3], or placebo [5,8]. Furthermore, enoxaparin was compared to dabigatran [11,12], edoxaban [6], and semuloprin [4], while deltaprin was compared to aspirin [10] or placebo [13]. The efficacy of low molecular weight heparin was assessed by Van Adrechem et al. in comparison to no treatment [7]. The dose of thromboprophylaxis was started postoperatively in most of the included studies [5-10,12,13], while it was used pre and postoperatively in other studies [3,4,11].

The thromboprophylaxis effect was higher when rivaroxaban compared to no treatment or placebo [3,5], while no significant differences were found when rivaroxaban [8], dalteparin [13] or low-molecular-weight heparin [7] compared to placebo.

Moreover, when medications compared to each other, no significant difference in thromboprophylaxis effect was reported in many included studies [4,9,10,12]. Only edoxaban and dabigatran were found superior to enoxaparin by Fuji et al. [6] and Eriksson et al. [11], respectively.

DISCUSSION:

Oral anticoagulants were used to reduce risk of thromboembolism following major operation such as knee and hip surgery [14]. Recently, new drugs have been introduced in order to overcome the adverse effects associated with warfarin such as edoxaban, rivaroxaban, enoxaparin, dabigatran, daltparin, and low-molecular-weight heparin [15,16]. This review aimed to assess the evidence supporting use of these new medications as thromboprophylaxis.

The proper dose of these medications depends on patients' characteristics such as age, obesity, and renal function. In the included studies, when rivaroxaban compared to placebo, it showed a significant prophylactic efficacy in studies conducted by Camporese et al.[5] and Li et al. [3] despite of different mean age of patients recruited in each study. Mean age of patients in the study of Lie et al. was 76.1 in comparison to 44.9 in Camporese et al. study. Despite of small sample size in the study Li et al. [3], patients were old with several risk factors such as diabetes, hypertension and previous history of VTE. Thus, anticoagulant prophylactic therapy before and after surgery showed a higher significant eeficacy when compared to no treatment. Most of the comparison

between medications showed no superiority except when edoxaban and dabigatran compared to enoxaparin by Fuji et al. [6] and Eriksson et al. [11], respectively. Obesity was the risk factor reported by both studies and the results were not adjusted for other risk factors. The adjustment of the confounding effect of other risk factors could change the findings of the studies. In the study conducted by Eriksson et al., the sample size was 2055 patients and in such large sample small difference can show statistical significance even with very small clinical difference [11].

Along with the advantages of these new medications, concerns about the complications such as bleeding episodes will arise. The surveillance reported elevated risk of hemorrhage among elderlies and patients with renal failure [17]. Therefore, an age and other risk factors such as hypertension, diabetes mellitus, hormonal therapy and history of major bleeding should be included in the recommendations of NOACs' dose modification [18].

CONCLUSION:

This review showed that new oral anticoagulants could be effective in reducing risk of thrombosis particularly in high-risk patients subjected to major surgery. Rivaroxaban had a higher efficacy than placebo in preventing thrombosis after major surgeries particularly in old patients or those with predisposing factors such as obesity, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, coronary heart diseases, and hormonal therapy.

Study	Study design	Sample size	Age of patients (mean±SD)	Type of surgery	Underlying risk factor	Prophylactic medications	Time of administration	Comparison medication	Effectiveness of thromboprophylaxis
[3]	A randomized controlled trial	80	76.1	Femoral neck fracture	History of VTE Hypertension Diabetes Smoking	Rivaroxaban 10mg once daily	Preoperative/postoperative	Patients did not receive prophylaxis before surgery	The incidence of preoperative DVT was significantly lower in the oral rivaroxaban group than in the conservative treatment group
[9]	A randomized clinical trial	194	66.8±7.4	Total Knee Replacement	Hypertension Coronary heart disease Diabetes	Rivaroxaban	Postoperative	Enoxaparin	There were 4 patients with DVT (3 posterior tibial vein, 1 peroneal vein) in enoxaparin, 0 patients in group rivaroxaban, and the difference was not statistically significant (p=.121).
[7]	A multicenter, randomized, controlled, open-label trials with blinded outcome evaluation	1543	46.0±16.5	Knee Arthroscopy and Lower-Leg Casting	Obesity Smoking Contraceptive use	A prophylactic dose of low-molecular-weight heparin	Postoperative (for the 8 days after arthroscopy)	No anticoagulant therapy	Venous thromboembolism occurred in 5 of the 731 patients (0.7%) in the treatment group and in 3 of the 720 patients (0.4%) in the control group (relative risk, 1.6; 95% confidence interval [CI], 0.4 to 6.8;
[8]	A Double-Blind Randomized Clinical Trial	198	68.19 ±6.62	Total Knee Arthroplasty	Not reported	Rivaroxaban 10 mg	Postoperative (each day for 14 doses postoperatively)	Placebo	There was no symptomatic deep-vein thrombosis or pulmonary embolism in either group
[12]	A prospective, double-blind, double-dummy study	179	47.7 ±14.4	Elective total hip arthroplasty	Obesity	Dabigatran 220 mg oral once daily, starting with a 110 mg half-dose, 1e4 hours after surgery	Postoperative	Subcutaneous enoxaparin 40 mg once daily, starting the evening before	Total VTE and all-cause mortality occurred in 18.7% of patients in the dabigatran group and 13.7% in the enoxaparin group [odds ratio 1.4 (95% confidence

								surgery	interval 0.6, 3.5)].
[19]	A phase II, multicenter, double-blind, placebo-controlled randomized study	241	44.9 ±12.8	Knee arthroscopy	Obesity Diabetes Hormonal treatment Hyperlipaemia Hypertension	Rivaroxaban	Postoperative	Placebo	The primary efficacy outcome occurred in 120/1 of the rivaroxaban group and in 7/114 of the placebo group (p=0.03; crude relative risk 0.14, 95 % CI, 0.02 to 0.83)
[13]	A multicenter, double-blind trial	265	48.8±16.3	Surgical repair of unilateral or bilateral, closed or open fractures of the tibia, fibula, or ankle	Not reported	Dalteparin 5000 units	Postoperative	Placebo	Overall, only 5 patients developed CIVTE (1.9%, 95% confidence interval: 0.7 to 4.7), 2 in the dalteparin group and 3 in the placebo group (1.5% vs. 2.3%, P = 0.68)
[6]	A randomized, double-blind, double-dummy study	716	72.6±7.5	Total Knee Arthroplasty	Obesity	Oral edoxaban 30 mg once daily	Postoperative (beginning 6 to 24 hours after surgery)	Enoxaparin 2000 IU (equivalent to 20 mg) subcutaneously twice daily beginning 24 to 36 hours postoperative for 11 to 14 days	Superiority (P=0.010) of edoxaban versus enoxaparin
[4]	A multinational, randomized, double-blind, double dummy, parallel group study	4413	62	Major laparotomy	Obesity Chronic heart failure Chronic respiratory failure Hormone therapy	Daily enoxaparin 40 mg	Preoperative/postoperative	Daily semuloparin 20 mg	The primary endpoint of any VTE or all-cause death occurred in 97 of 1531 (6.3%) patients receiving semuloparin and in 82 of 1499 (5.5%) patients receiving enoxaparin (OR=1.16, 95% CI: 0.84–1.59)

[10]	A multicenter randomized, controlled trial	778	57.9 (12.2)	Elective unilateral total hip arthroplasty	Hypertension Diabetes Hyperlipidemia	After an initial 10 days of dalteparin prophylaxis after elective surgery, patients were randomly assigned to 28 days of dalteparin	Postoperative	Aspirin	Aspirin was noninferior (P = 0.001) but not superior (P = 0.22) to dalteparin
[11]	A randomized, double-blind, non-inferiority trial	2,055	62 ± 12	Total hip arthroplasty	Obesity	Oral dabigatran, 220 mg once-daily, starting with a half-dose 1–4 hours after surgery	Preoperative/postoperative	Subcutaneous enoxaparin 40 mg once-daily, starting the evening before surgery	The primary efficacy outcome occurred in 7.7% of the dabigatran group versus 8.8% of the enoxaparin group, risk difference (RD) -1.1% (95%CI -3.8 to 1.6%)

Table (1): The efficacy of medications used as thromboprophylaxis following surgical procedures reported by included studies in the review

REFERENCES:

1. Weitz JI. Emerging anticoagulants for the treatment of venous thromboembolism. *Thrombosis and haemostasis* 2006;96(03):274-84.
2. Huel NH, Nar H, Priepe H, Ries U, Stassen J-M, Wiene W. Structure-based design of novel potent nonpeptide thrombin inhibitors. *Journal of medicinal chemistry* 2002;45(9):1757-66.
3. Li Q, Dai B, Xu J, Yao Y, Song K, Zhang H et al. Can patients with femoral neck fracture benefit from preoperative thromboprophylaxis?: A prospective randomized controlled trial. *Medicine* 2017;96(29)
4. Kakkar AK, Agnelli G, Fisher W, George D, Lassen MR, Mismetti P et al. Preoperative enoxaparin versus postoperative semuloparin thromboprophylaxis in major abdominal surgery: a randomized controlled trial. *Annals of surgery* 2014;259(6):1073-9.
5. Camporese G, Bernardi E, Noventa F, Bosco M, Monteleone G, Santoro L et al. Efficacy of Rivaroxaban for thromboprophylaxis after Knee Arthroscopy (ERIKA). *Thrombosis and haemostasis* 2016;116(08):349-55.
6. Fuji T, Wang C-J, Fujita S, Kawai Y, Nakamura M, Kimura T et al. Safety and efficacy of edoxaban, an oral factor Xa inhibitor, versus enoxaparin for thromboprophylaxis after total knee arthroplasty: the STARS E-3 trial. *Thrombosis research* 2014;134(6):1198-204.
7. van Adrichem RA, Nemeth B, Algra A, le Cessie S, Rosendaal FR, Schipper IB et al. Thromboprophylaxis after knee arthroscopy and lower-leg casting. *New England Journal of Medicine* 2017;376(6):515-25.
8. Wang J-W, Chen B, Lin P-C, Yen S-H, Huang C-C, Kuo F-C. The efficacy of combined use of rivaroxaban and tranexamic acid on blood conservation in minimally invasive total knee arthroplasty a double-blind randomized, controlled trial. *The Journal of arthroplasty* 2017;32(3):801-6.
9. Xie J, Ma J, Huang Q, Yue C, Pei F. Comparison of enoxaparin and rivaroxaban in balance of anti-fibrinolysis and anticoagulation following primary total knee replacement: a pilot study. *Medical science monitor: international medical journal of experimental and clinical research* 2017;23:704.
10. Anderson DR, Dunbar MJ, Bohm ER, Belzile E, Kahn SR, Zukor D et al. Aspirin versus low-molecular-weight heparin for extended venous thromboembolism prophylaxis after total hip arthroplasty: a randomized trial. *Annals of internal medicine* 2013;158(11):800-6.
11. Eriksson BI, Dahl OE, Huo MH, Kurth AA, Hantel S, Hermansson K et al. Oral dabigatran versus enoxaparin for thromboprophylaxis after primary total hip arthroplasty (RE-NOVATE II). *Thrombosis and haemostasis* 2011;106(04):721-9.
12. Malhotra R, Babhulkar S, Sanjib KB, Clemens A, Dadi A, Iyer R et al. Thromboprophylaxis with dabigatran after total hip arthroplasty in Indian patients: A subanalysis of a double-blind, double-dummy, randomized RE-NOVATE II study. *Asian journal of surgery* 2017;40(2):145-51.
13. Selby R, Geerts WH, Kreder HJ, Crowther MA, Kaus L, Sealey F. A double-blind, randomized controlled trial of the prevention of clinically important venous thromboembolism after isolated lower leg fractures. *Journal of orthopaedic trauma* 2015;29(5):224-30.
14. Eriksson B, Dahl O, Rosencher N, Kurth A, van Dijk CN, Frostick S et al. Oral dabigatran etexilate vs. subcutaneous enoxaparin for the prevention of venous thromboembolism after total knee replacement: the RE-MODEL randomized trial. *Journal of Thrombosis and Haemostasis* 2007;5(11):2178-85.
15. Young AM, Marshall A, Thirlwall J, Chapman O, Lokare A, Hill C et al. Comparison of an oral factor Xa inhibitor with low molecular weight heparin in patients with cancer with venous thromboembolism: results of a randomized trial (SELECT-D). *Journal of Clinical Oncology* 2018;36(20)
16. Samama MM, Gerotziafas GT. Newer anticoagulants in 2009. *Journal of thrombosis and thrombolysis* 2010;29(1):92.
17. Chowdhry U, Jacques A, Karovitch A, Giguère P, Nguyen M-L. Appropriateness of dabigatran and rivaroxaban prescribing for hospital inpatients. *The Canadian journal of hospital pharmacy* 2016;69(3):194.
18. Pharithi RB, Ranganathan D, O'Brien J, Egom EE, Burke C, Ryan D et al. Is the prescription right? A review of non-vitamin K antagonist anticoagulant (NOAC) prescriptions in patients with non-valvular atrial fibrillation. Safe prescribing in atrial fibrillation and evaluation of non-vitamin K oral anticoagulants in stroke prevention (SAFE-NOACS) group. *Irish Journal of Medical Science (1971-)* 2018:1-8.
19. Camporese G, Bernardi E, Noventa F, Bosco M, Monteleone G, Santoro L et al. Efficacy of Rivaroxaban for thromboprophylaxis after Knee Arthroscopy (ERIKA). *Thrombosis and haemostasis* 2016;116(2):349-55.